

ISic0703

I.Sicily inscription 0703

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di

Catania, inventory 333

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] aelio [---]

2. [---] mo ma[---]

3. [---] ç,ilio · St[---]

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285102

EDCS 6100268

EDCS 16200484

Bibliography

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